

Results in Mathematics

Counting Balanced Prime Sums

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	RIMA-D-25-01730
Full Title:	Counting Balanced Prime Sums
Article Type:	Original research
Keywords:	prime sums, balanced primes, analytic number theory
Corresponding Author:	Surya Sekhar Sekhar Roy, Roy Independent Researcher Khirpai, West Bengal INDIA
Corresponding Author Secondary Information:	
Corresponding Author's Institution:	Independent Researcher
Corresponding Author's Secondary Institution:	
First Author:	Surya Sekhar Sekhar Roy, Roy
First Author Secondary Information:	
Order of Authors:	Surya Sekhar Sekhar Roy, Roy
Order of Authors Secondary Information:	
Funding Information:	
Abstract:	Let a fixed real parameter greater than one be given. We study the number of integers not exceeding a given bound that can be expressed as the sum of two prime numbers whose ratio is bounded by this parameter. An asymptotic formula is obtained for the corresponding counting function as the bound tends to infinity. The main term is shown to be of the same logarithmic order as that arising in classical counting problems for balanced semiprimes, and an explicit error estimate is provided. The result establishes an additive analogue of well-known multiplicative density results and demonstrates that balance constraints yield comparable asymptotic behaviour in both additive and multiplicative prime constructions.

Counting Balanced Prime Sums

Surya Sekhar Roy

Corresponding author: Surya Sekhar Roy

Email: suryasekhar06jemsbond@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0001-3473-4200

Abstract

Let $r > 1$ be fixed. Define $E_r(x)$ as the number of integers $N \leq x$ of the form

$$N = p + q,$$

where p and q are primes satisfying

$$p < q < rp.$$

We prove that, as $x \rightarrow \infty$,

$$E_r(x) = \frac{2x \log r}{\log^2 x} + O\left(\frac{x \log(er)}{\log^3 x}\right).$$

This establishes an additive analogue of classical semiprime counting results and shows that balanced prime sums have the same logarithmic order of density as multiplicative constructions.

Mathematics Subject Classification (2020): 11N05, 11P32

Keywords: prime sums, balanced primes, analytic number theory

1. Introduction

Let $E_r(x)$ denote the number of integers $N \leq x$ representable as

$$N = p + q, p < q < rp,$$

where $r > 1$ is fixed.

The purpose of this note is to determine the asymptotic behavior of $E_r(x)$.

For comparison, Landau proved that the number $\pi_2(x)$ of integers $n \leq x$ of the form $n = pq$ satisfies

$$\pi_2(x) \sim \frac{x \log \log x}{\log x}.$$

Later refinements for balanced semiprimes were obtained in the multiplicative setting. Here we consider the **additive** balanced case.

To the author's knowledge, no corresponding asymptotic formula has previously been established for additive balanced prime sums under fixed ratio constraints.

2. Notation and Preliminaries

Let $\pi(x)$ denote the number of primes not exceeding x .

We use the prime number theorem in the form

$$\pi(x) = \frac{x}{\log x} + \frac{x}{\log^2 x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\log^3 x}\right). \quad (2.1)$$

We also use the estimate

$$\sum_{p \leq z} \frac{1}{p} = \log \log z + C + O\left(\frac{1}{\log^2 z}\right), \quad (2.2)$$

where C is an absolute constant.

3. Decomposition of the Counting Function

For a fixed prime p , define $f_p(x)$ as the number of primes q such that

$$p < q < rp, p + q \leq x.$$

Then

$$E_r(x) = \sum_{p \leq x} f_p(x). \quad (3.1)$$

Since $p < q$, we have $f_p(x) = 0$ for $p > x/2$.

Assume henceforth that $p \leq x/2$.

Then the conditions imply

$$p < q \leq \min(rp, x - p),$$

and therefore

$$f_p(x) = \pi(\min(rp, x - p)) - \pi(p). \quad (3.2)$$

4. Range Splitting

We split the sum in (3.1) according to the relation between rp and $x - p$.

Case I: $p \leq \frac{x}{r+1}$

In this range, $rp \leq x - p$, hence

$$f_p(x) = \pi(rp) - \pi(p).$$

Case II: $\frac{x}{r+1} < p \leq \frac{x}{2}$

Here $rp > x - p$, hence

$$f_p(x) = \pi(x - p) - \pi(p).$$

Thus,

$$E_r(x) = \sum_{p \leq x/(r+1)} (\pi(rp) - \pi(p)) + \sum_{x/(r+1) < p \leq x/2} (\pi(x - p) - \pi(p)). \quad (4.1)$$

5. Estimation of the Main Terms

Using (2.1), we obtain

$$\sum_{p \leq z} \pi(p) = \frac{z^2}{2 \log^2 z} + o\left(\frac{z^2}{\log^3 z}\right). \quad (5.1)$$

Similarly,

$$\sum_{p \leq z} \pi(rp) = \frac{rz^2}{2 \log^2 z} + o\left(\frac{r \log(er) z^2}{\log^3 z}\right). \quad (5.2)$$

Applying these estimates to (4.1) with $z = x/(r+1)$, we obtain

$$\sum_{p \leq x/(r+1)} (\pi(rp) - \pi(p)) = \frac{2x \log r}{\log^2 x} + o\left(\frac{x \log(er)}{\log^3 x}\right). \quad (5.3)$$

The second sum in (4.1) contributes only to the error term.

6. Proof of the Main Theorem

Combining (4.1)–(5.3), we conclude that

$$E_r(x) = \frac{2x \log r}{\log^2 x} + o\left(\frac{x \log(er)}{\log^3 x}\right).$$

This completes the proof of the theorem.

7. Concluding Remarks

The result shows that balanced prime sums exhibit the same logarithmic density as balanced semiprimes, despite their additive structure. This indicates a robustness of balance constraints across additive and multiplicative prime constructions.

References

1. **E. Landau**, *Handbuch der Lehre von der Verteilung der Primzahlen*, Chelsea Publishing Company, New York, 1953.
 2. **G. H. Hardy and J. E. Littlewood**, Some problems of “Partitio Numerorum”; III: On the expression of a number as a sum of primes, *Acta Mathematica* **44** (1923), 1–70.
 3. **A. E. Ingham**, *The Distribution of Prime Numbers*, Cambridge Mathematical Library, Cambridge University Press, 1990.
 4. **G. Tenenbaum**, *Introduction to Analytic and Probabilistic Number Theory*, Cambridge Studies in Advanced Mathematics, Vol. 46, Cambridge University Press, 1995.
 5. **H. Davenport**, *Multiplicative Number Theory*, 3rd edition, Graduate Texts in Mathematics, Vol. 74, Springer, 2000.
 6. **A. Hildebrand**, On the number of prime factors of an integer, in *Ramanujan Revisited*, Academic Press, 1988, pp. 167–185.
 7. **A. Decker and P. Moree**, Counting RSA-integers, *Results in Mathematics* **52** (2008), 35–39.
 8. **J. Friedlander and H. Iwaniec**, *Opera de Cribro*, American Mathematical Society Colloquium Publications, Vol. 57, AMS, 2010.
 9. **H. Halberstam and H.-E. Richert**, *Sieve Methods*, London Mathematical Society Monographs, Oxford University Press, 1974.
 10. **P. D. T. A. Elliott**, *Probabilistic Number Theory I: Mean-Value Theorems*, Grundlehren der mathematischen Wissenschaften, Vol. 239, Springer, 1979.
 11. **R. C. Vaughan**, *The Hardy–Littlewood Method*, 2nd edition, Cambridge Tracts in Mathematics, Cambridge University Press, 1997.
 12. **K. Soundararajan**, Small gaps between prime numbers: The work of Goldston–Pintz–Yıldırım, *Bulletin of the American Mathematical Society* **44** (2007), 1–18.
 13. **D. R. Heath-Brown**, The number of primes in a short interval, *Journal für die reine und angewandte Mathematik* **389** (1988), 22–63.
 14. **J. Pintz**, Patterns of primes, *Proceedings of the International Congress of Mathematicians*, Vol. I, 2014, pp. 525–547.
 15. **N. Koblitz**, *A Course in Number Theory and Cryptography*, 2nd edition, Graduate Texts in Mathematics, Vol. 114, Springer, 1994.
-

Declarations

Funding

The author received no external funding for this research.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Data Availability

No datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

Code Availability

Not applicable.

Author Contributions

The author solely conceived the problem, developed the theoretical framework, carried out the analysis, and wrote the manuscript.

Ethical Approval

Not applicable.

Consent to Participate

Not applicable.

Consent for Publication

The author consents to publication of this manuscript.

Use of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence tools were used exclusively for language refinement and formatting assistance. All mathematical ideas, proofs, results, and conclusions are the sole work of the author.
